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To cite this article: Wojtek Jezierski (03 Nov 2023): St Adalbert as a stranger-king: The heroization and estrangement of a holy man in the Middle Ages, History and Anthropology, DOI: [10.1080/02757206.2023.2275786](https://doi.org/10.1080/02757206.2023.2275786)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02757206.2023.2275786>

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Published online: 03 Nov 2023.

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St Adalbert as a stranger-king: The heroization and estrangement of a holy man in the Middle Ages

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ABSTRACT

There was no holy king in Poland during the Middle Ages. Although the Piast polity belonged to the North-eastern European periphery (East-Central Europe and Scandinavia), where essentially all post-1000 CE polities boasted dynastic martyred holy rulers of native origin, the Piasts never elevated a member of their kin to such a position. The present article takes this puzzling exception as a point of departure to advance the argument that the episcopal holy patron of Poland of Bohemian origin – St Adalbert (c. 956–997) – may in many regards be interpreted as a version of Marshall Sahlins's *stranger-king*. By combining anthropological theory and comparative evidence, the article explores the locally produced hagiographical sources from the twelfth to the fifteenth centuries in order to demonstrate how St Adalbert's heroic status and retroactively invented ethnic and sacral otherness were exploited for the purposes of institutional and king-like legitimacy vis-à-vis the Polish people. In its conclusions the article argues that concepts and comparative methods from political anthropology can help us to reconsider the category of holy rulers and offer new ways of reading hagiographical sources as political treatises.

KEYWORDS

Holy rulers; stranger-kings; St Adalbert; medieval Poland; hagiography; otherness

If he is a King then where is his crown? I've got a crown, got a very nice one and it's here on my head. Look at it. Have I got it on? (King Julien XIII, *Madagascar* (2005), dir. Eric Darnell, Tom McGrath)

Introduction

To state the obvious, which nonetheless remains a millennium-old riddle: there was no holy ruler in Poland during the Middle Ages. Almost from the onset of the Christianization of the North-eastern fringes of Europe (East-Central Europe and Scandinavia), the figures of holy rulers emerged, in the eyes of scholars, as an almost *sine qua non* of both dynastic

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politics and the formation of peripheral states. Typically within thirty to hundred years of the incorporation of the local elites into the sphere of the European *Christianitas*, the ruling dynasties, often acting in close cooperation with their local churches, sanctified and created political cults focused on the martyred members of their own kin and adopted them as the patron saints of their emerging polities. Everywhere you look you find holy rulers whose cults were established in the High Middle Ages: St Wenceslas of Bohemia (d. 929/935), St Stephen of Hungary (d. 1038), Sts Boris and Gleb of Kyivan Rus' (d. c. 1015–1019), St Olaf Haraldsson of Norway (d. 1030), St Knud (d. 1086) and St Knud Lavard of Denmark (d. 1131), or St Erik of Sweden (d. 1160) (Antonsson and Garipzanov 2010; Bartlett 2013, 211–216, Berend 2007; Hoffmann 1975; Klaniczay 2002; Petersohn 1994; Steinsland 2000). Everywhere, but Poland.

Considered against the North-eastern European background and the general trends, the absence of a native holy ruler in Poland has perplexed medievalists since at least the 1960s (Górski 1968). Why did the Piasts not follow suit? How come the Piast dynasty and the Gniezno archbishopric (established in 1000 in Greater Poland) seemed to be content to claim that St Adalbert (known also as St Vojtěch/Wojciech, b. 956) – an exiled bishop of Prague martyred by the pagan Prussians in 997, who was a foreigner with a tenuous connection to the Polish elites but whose corpse the Piasts happened to possess – was their sole patron saint? He remained so until 1253, when the martyred St Bishop Stanislaus of Kraków (d. 1079) was canonized and began to share the role as Poland's patron saint (Kuzmová 2013; Labuda 2000). The proposed solutions to this riddle have a rich literature (summarized in Pac 2016), whose many turns need not be restated here. The current scholarly consensus seems to rest with the somewhat functionalistic explanation offered by Aleksander Gieysztor (1994, 332). He claimed that for the Piast dynasty, the Gniezno archbishopric and the Polish elites for a long time it was neither necessary nor viable to sanctify any of their members. It was simply that the position of the national patron saint had been filled from the very end of the tenth century by a person who combined the attributes of a monk, a martyr bishop of high elite origin, and a close collaborator of the German Emperor Otto III (r. 996–1002) and Duke Bolesław I Chrobry (the Brave, r. 992–1025, as king 1025). St Adalbert ticked all the boxes, so to speak, except for those concerning a royal title and an autochthonous origin, that is.¹

In this article I do not argue, as it has been done previously, that the Piasts might have entertained the idea of sanctifying their first king, Bolesław I Chrobry. The evidence for such claims is very weak (Janiak 2003; Pac 2016). Answering the question of why the Piasts did not elevate one of their own kin to the position of holy ruler is essentially impossible and thus uninteresting. As Ian Beuermann's (2014) study which sought to explain the absence of a holy king in the Kingdom of Man and the Isles vis-à-vis the Scandinavian background inadvertently shows, even if we stipulate the personal, political and cultural criteria for the appointment of holy rulers and check which of these were met (or not), such an approach can only take us so far in answering counterfactual questions. Absences of phenomena – even when framed through functionalistic or structural symmetry – are exceedingly difficult to explain. The goal of the current article is thus entirely different. My contention is that in certain regards St Adalbert himself can be interpreted as a royal saint – or, rather, that his medieval saintly image incorporated several traits and relationships typical of holy rulers. Specifically, I argue that St Adalbert can be viewed

as an example of a *stranger-king* in the way this concept was coined by the anthropologist Marshall Sahlins. To flesh out this claim, in what follows I explore how the saint's otherness and heroic status were exploited for the purposes of institutional, political and king-like legitimization in a selection of Polish high- and late-medieval hagiographical and historiographical texts.

Conceptually speaking, it is worth pointing out that the category of medieval holy rulers is not completely coherent or reducible to one ideal type. There was never a single model of a holy king on the post-1000 CE North-eastern periphery either. The circumstances of their deaths and the reasons for the sanctification of the dynastic saints, enumerated above, were historically highly variable. For the purposes of this article I thus consider holy rulers as conceptual assortment with, occasionally, mutually exclusive traits, a group which was connected by family resemblances rather than a closed set with fixed criteria (Klaniczay 2002, 62–194, 2010, 287–289; Nelson 1973).

Such a conceptual approach is crucial for the comparative methodology employed here, which makes parallels and juxtapositions between St Adalbert and other stranger-kings and peripheral holy kings in form of an unrestricted, or unbound, comparison. As Nick Cheesman (2021, 71–76) argues, an unbound comparison moves between empirical *comparanda* and translations from anthropological theory to medieval contexts. In this sense, the present article combines two types of comparison: perspectival and juxtapositional (Schaffer 2021, 48–50, 52–54). The former works by drawing analogies from an external conceptual perspective – Sahlins's political anthropology in this case – to tease out stranger-king traits in St Adalbert's hagiographical image. This approach also follows Caroline Walker Bynum's (2020, 40–47, 183–220; see also: Lincoln 2018, 25–27, 40–41, 109, 153) recent suggestion that scholars should focus on the types of the presence of the holy and the locations of its agency as a way of identifying similarities of sacrality – and their political implications, I would add – across disparate domains and cultures. The second, juxtapositional type of comparison works by identifying parallels between St Adalbert and other contemporary peripheral holy kings. To narrow down the latter's comparative scope, however, I follow Sverre Bagge's (2006, 511–512; see also: Antonsson, 2010, 18–23; Klaniczay 2010, 299–301; Jezierski, Orning, and Pac, 2024) compelling suggestion that the closest parallel to the two missionary men, Bolesław I and St Adalbert, who shaped the process of Christianization in Poland – and in the context of which the latter's mythical stranger-kingship emerges – are the near-contemporary Norwegian missionary rulers and counterparts, Olaf I Tryggvason (r. 995–1000) and St Olaf II Haraldsson (r. 1015–1028, d. 1030).

Caveat emptor: this article does not propose a wholesale revamping of St Adalbert. As many scholars have shown, the saint reliably remained the crucial political patron saint in Poland throughout the Middle Ages and the rich and variable sources that promote his image and memory present no evidence of his explicit royalization. There are, for instance, no depictions of him wearing a royal crown, holding a scepter, or sitting on a throne, nor was he ever given a similar title to St Olaf's posthumous appellation as *rex perpetuus Norvegiæ*, the eternal king of Norway (Labuda 1997; 2004; Węcowski 2014, 297–321; Wood 2001, 207–225). The sources and episodes selected for this study, though they are absolutely central for St Adalbert's cult in Poland, represent a sliver excerpted from a larger hagiographical corpus. However, when interpreted through the stranger-king framework this representative and important sample does reveal a series of hitherto

underappreciated royal-like traits and parallels between St Adalbert, other contemporary holy rulers, and stranger-kings from non-European cultures. By adding the anthropological perspective to the medievalist discussion, this article's approach is experimental and corrective rather than radically revisionist. It aims to broaden our understanding of the category of medieval holy rulers and our ways of approaching the problem of sacrality of political power through conceptual and disciplinary crosspollination.

St Adalbert on Fiji, or what is a stranger-king

Let us sketch out the central analytical concept here, whose details will be augmented in the discussion of the source material below. As Sahlins (2008, 178; see also: de Heusch, 1991) notes

from ancient to modern times, the rulers of a remarkable number of societies around the world have been strangers to the places and people they rule. By their dynastic origins and their inherited nature, as rehearsed in ongoing traditions and royal rituals, they are foreigners – who on that ground must concede certain privileges to the native people.

Such kings, David Graeber and Sahlins (2017, 70) add, 'not only try to mark themselves as exterior to society, but actually claim to (...) at the very least to derive from ancestors who do'. In that way, 'there is a sense almost everywhere that "society", however conceived, is not self-sufficient; that power, creative energy – life, even – ultimately comes from outside. On the other hand, raw power', which such stranger-kings embody, 'needs to be domesticated. In myth, this often leads to stories of wild, destructive young conquerors who arrive from far away, only to be eventually tamed on marriage to "daughters of the land." In rituals, it often leads to ceremonies in which the king is himself conquered by the people.' Finally,

notable in the Fijian account is the ambiguous mixture of contract and chicane attending the transfer of power from the original 'owners' of the land (*i taukei*) to their parvenu rulers. Something similar is almost always found in these foundational traditions, usually including demonstrations of violence on the part of the stranger – which will turn out to have positive values for the indigenous people. (Sahlins 2008, 179)

Sahlins developed the notion of stranger-kings based on his ethnographic work in Fiji and Polynesia, which he later expanded with examples from other regions. Building on the comparative mythology and studies of dynastic foundation myths, particularly those studied, among others, by Georges Dumézil (1988). Sahlins (2008) concluded that stranger-kings constitute an elementary form of political life, which is nearly universal in scope. The conviction of the necessary potency of alterity condensed in the figure of stranger-kings appears to underpin the innumerable origin stories of polities, societies and kinship groups in prehistorical, historical and contemporary contexts (Graeber and Wengrow 2021, 334–336).

Based on his study of exotic elements and foreign rulership in Viking burials and origin myths, Andres Siegfried Dobat (2015, 164–165) also stresses that in the stranger-king phenomenon 'the mythical king is associated with important technological inventions, laws or new forms of social and political organization'. These last two aspects are crucial for St Adalbert's case. As an archaeologist, Dobat (2015, 165) zeroes in on the

material and symbolic media such as *monuments* and *ceremonies* that evoke and reproduce the stranger-kingship as a narrative about the immigrant king or forefather who took the possession of the locals' land and founded the dynasty. For historians' purposes, however, these material expressions can be substituted with *stories* that evoke such actions.

Though Sahlins's concept has had very little success among medievalists (and none among students of medieval holy rulers), the purported external origins of many medieval rulers and dynasties have long been explored through dynastic legends with inspiration from Dumézil (for example Banaszekiewicz 2010; Brady 2022; Plassmann 2006; Třeštík 1997). What Dobat's article and Jonas Wellendorf's (2022a, 2022b) philological studies of Old Norse origin myths share with the investigations by historians is that they tend to locate and explore stories about stranger-kings in prehistoric, legendary and mythical times (Weiler 2015). Exploring St Adalbert as a special case of a stranger-king who had some traits of a holy ruler, a hybrid of the two types essentially, can thus be illuminating for several interconnected reasons. One, because in contrast to the above-mentioned peripheral holy kings, all of whom were of autochthonous descent, he was a bishop and a stranger to the people over whom he was supposed to rule. Two, because in contrast to the mythical stranger-kings, St Adalbert was a historical figure, and though his otherness was initially not seen as a problem, it was creatively augmented and utilized later through a process of a retroactive mythologization of his persona. Three, because in contrast to the usual dynastic mythologies deriving from a *long time ago*, the sources concerning St Adalbert come from an extended but delineated period of time: from his lifetime, closely following his death and from centuries later. This means we can observe from close up how the process of making him a stranger-king unfolded and how his mythologization was inserted into historical time.

Sources of otherness and other sources

As the above discussion shows, the figure of the stranger-king only makes sense when considered from the viewpoint of an indigenous community, to which a foreign ruler arrives from the outside. For this reason, in terms of the hagiographical and historiographical sources, the corpus selected for this study consists of those produced locally in Poland. Moreover, I focus only on those texts (Węcowski 2014, 297–321) where St Adalbert's status as a stranger is most pronounced and explicitly exploited for political and institutional legitimization purposes. As scholars have shown (Allport 2022; Sahlins 2012; Wellendorf 2022a, 514–523), such selective treatment is justified because in many traditions a plurality of beliefs about the allochthonous or autochthonous origins of power and the elites can exist side by side informing each other or evolving over time.

The hagiographical texts concerning St Adalbert came in several waves. The two well-explored texts of the first wave were penned outside Poland that were written soon after the martyr's death in 997, which attest to the international and imperial fame Adalbert enjoyed in life and in death. These were the *Vita prior*, which was composed c. 999 at the request of Emperor Otto III and is usually attributed to Johannes Canaparius, the abbot of SS. Boniface and Alexius in Rome, who personally met Adalbert. The second is

the *Vita altera* by Bruno of Querfurt, composed in two redactions in 1004 and 1008 (Karwasińska 1996; Labuda 2004, 16–21; Sosnowski 2013; Wood 2001, 207–225). Even though this first wave, based on St Adalbert's followers' eye-witness accounts, was central for how the saint was to be portrayed later, it will be largely disregarded here. It is because: firstly, these texts do not reflect the home-grown representation of the saint; secondly, neither of them tells us anything about the relationship between the saint and the Polish people whose patron he was to become; and thirdly neither of them describes any form of otherness for St Adalbert vis-à-vis the Polish community. It is important to mention these texts, however, because they continued to be copied in Poland throughout the Middle Ages, and because through them we can verify how subsequent authors went about mythologizing and heroizing the stranger saint. In addition to this first wave the brief *Passio s. Adalperti martiris* (also known as *Passio from Tegernsee*) should be noted; it was written in Poland before 1025. Based on the accounts of the saint's companions the text represents (Karwasińska 1962; Sosnowski 2013, 158–191) an initial local take on St Adalbert's image, in which no traces of his stranger-kingship can be found as it does not exploit his alterity either.

What primarily interests me here are several episodes from the second wave of hagiographies of St Adalbert that were penned in Poland in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, particularly the *Tempore illo* (1888; also known as *De sancto Adalberto episcopo*) and its later adaptation, the *Miracula sancti Adalberti* (Chłopocka 1997; Grzesik 1997; Gromadzki 1989; Labuda 2004, 33–36), which seem to reflect a wider trend of the mythologization of saints at that time (Praulzsch 2021). These two texts are anonymous, but they were created in the milieu of Gniezno. They combine the information from Bruno's *Vita altera* and specific redactions of the *Vita prior* and the *Passio from Tegernsee* with later, locally invented legends about the saint, which are the main focus of our interest here. Neither of these texts can be dated exactly. The current scholarly consensus states that the *Tempore illo* probably comes from the twelfth to the mid-thirteenth century (likely before 1248). The *Miracula* is usually dated to the second half of the thirteenth century, after 1248 (most likely after 1280) and before 1295, when King Przemysław II ascended to the Polish throne (the *Miracula* [1883, 9.37] state explicitly that after King Bolesław II the Bold (r. 1076–1079) 'until today there are no kings in Poland'). The latter text is a compilation of St Adalbert's life and miracles based on the *Tempore illo*, which contains a number of suggestive additions (Labuda 2004, 36–37). It is difficult to say with precision why these texts have been written, other than that they seem to represent the views of the Gniezno cathedral. Their purpose was therefore the promotion of a revamped vision of St Adalbert's life and actions which was intended to renew the metropolitan chapter's identification with the holy man.

In the penultimate section of this article, I study a re-telling of some of the episodes from the *Tempore illo* which were included in Jan Długosz's (Ioannes/Johannes Długosius, 1415–1480) *Annales seu cronicae incliti Regni Poloniae* from the mid-fifteenth century. Długosz is perhaps best known as a diplomat, the instructor of several of Jagiellonian heirs, and a candidate for the archbishoprics of Prague and Lviv in 1471 and 1479, respectively. What is crucial here is that when he wrote his *Annals*, Długosz was a canon at the archiepiscopal cathedral of Kraków (Knoll 1982), a milieu with which he was very closely identified. This identification, as we will see, had an important bearing on how he presented St Adalbert's fate in Poland.

The militarization and heroization of St Adalbert

Before I move on to discuss St Adalbert's stranger-kingship based on the hagiographical material, let me consider an early example of his heroization which echoes some attributes of other peripheral holy rulers. The story comes from the *Gesta Principum Polonorum*, a chronicle written between 1113 and 1116 in the milieu of the Polish episcopate and the court of Duke Bolesław III Wrymouth (Krzywousty, r. 1102–1138). The chronicler came to be referred to as Gallus Anonymous, due to his possible origin in France. Though neither the *Vita prior* nor the *Vita altera* presents St Adalbert as a warrior in life, the *Gesta* features a miracle from 1097, where the saint protected an unnamed Polish castle or hillfort from an attack by the pagan Pomeranians, who were the main collective enemies of Bolesław III when Gallus wrote his chronicle:

He who is ever watchful, who will never slumber, set the vigilance of his soldier Adalbert [*sui militis Adalberti*] to watch over the townsfolk as they slept, and unearthly arms struck terror in the pagans lying awake to ambush the Christians. For there appeared to the Pomeranians an armed figure mounted on a white horse, who with drawn sword [*quidam (...) armatus, qui gladio extracto territabat*] struck terror in them and drove them headlong down the castle steps (...) it was without doubt the protection of the glorious martyr Adalbert [*defensione gloriosi martiris Adalberti*] that thus rescued the [inhabitants] from imminent peril and death. (Gallus 2003, II.6.130–131)

This passage is first and foremost an adaptation of the motif of *miles* or *athleta Christi* as a figurative way of invoking St Adalbert's spiritual protection over the locals. However, I would like to suggest an extended reading which relates the military imagery and hagiographical motifs used here to that featured in the cults of other holy men of that same period. I will return to the interpretation of this excerpt shortly, but speaking in comparative terms the militarization of clergymen – also martyred clergymen – though not unheard-of, was relatively rare in the high-medieval Baltic Sea context. This tendency gained momentum with the introduction of the idea of holy war to this region, particularly after 1147, which married religious violence with intolerance against the pagans (Buc 2023, 125–129; Kotecki, Maciejewski, and Ott 2017). However, as Kurt Villads Jensen (2018, 2020) has demonstrated, saints who did go to war in the Baltic Sea region during the High Middle Ages were mostly holy kings of local origin, divine figures such as the Virgin Mary or the archangels, and only rarely universal holy clerics such as St Lawrence (known as St Lars in Scandinavia) or St Martin of Tours. The 1097 example may thus reflect the desire to present the Piasts' expeditions against Pomeranians as an exceptionally early case of crusading and holy war (von Güttner-Sporzyński 2014, 77–106; Kersken 2006) aided by Poland's patron saint. St Adalbert's early militarization – which admittedly only occurs in this one episode – would seem to be more reminiscent of the militarization of holy kings who had a warrior background, a phenomenon that stretches back to Antiquity (Bartlett 2013, 378–383; Graus 1977; Kantorowicz 1961; Prautzsch 2021, 184–231).

The paradigmatic case of the militarization of holy rulers in North-eastern Europe is St Olaf (d. 1030), who can be used here as a convenient comparison. The appropriation of Olaf's warrior status for religious purposes and the haloing of the future saint's military attributes is particularly visible in the Norwegian ecclesiastical sources (Bagge 2010, 300–304). Consider the following excerpt from the mid-twelfth-century *Passio Sancti*

Olavi that depicts the king on his journey through Sweden to return to Norway to reclaim his realm:

Clad in the breastplate of faith, girded with the sword of the spirit which is the word of God [‘Indutus igitur lorica fidei et accinctus gladio Spiritus’] (...) with the armor of righteousness on the right hand and the left, the illustrious preacher steadfastly sowed the word of faith wherever he went, ready to suffer any persecution for Christ’s sake. (*Passio et miracula* 2014, vol. 2, P.VIII.5.26; Kunin 2001, 30)

Soon thereafter, at Stiklestad where he met his martyrdom in 1030, Olaf may have been a reluctant warrior, but ‘the warfare was at hand which he, the lover of peace, undertook to fight for the sake of justice and equity’ (*Passio et miracula* 2014, vol. 2, P.IX.8.28; Kunin 2001, 31). This mutually reinforcing blend of the military status and the image of Olaf as *miles Christi* followed the king to his death. He ‘went joyously from a soldier’s camp to the King’s eternal palace, from battle to the peace of God’ (*Passio et miracula* 2014, vol. 2, P.X.2.29; Kunin 2001, 31). Also after his martyrdom, St Olaf continued to provide military services, as reported by both the ecclesiastical Latin and Old Norse secular sources. St Olaf did this by visiting his warring confessors and royal successors in their dreams to assist them with advice or by appearing in front of their armies to personally lead their troops on the battlefield, particularly during battles against pagans. He did this for an anonymous Norwegian chieftain fighting in Ireland, in 1043 for his son Magnus the Good, for Emperor Alexios I Komnenos, and for King Sverre Sigurdsson, to name just a few (*Passio et miracula* 2014, vol. 2, 30–35; Snorri Sturlusson 1941, *Magnúss saga ins Góða*, vol. 3, 27.43, *Hákonar saga Herdibreids*, vol. 3, 21.371–372; *Ágrip* 1985, 38.36–37, 50.221–223; *Sverris saga* 2007, 5.8). St Olaf’s protective and military actions thus seem to have been associated with and helped individual royal or warrior figures who were similar to St Olaf himself (Jensen 2018). Within the confines of Norwegian politics, particularly during the civil war period (1130s–1240s), the saint’s military assistance was also quite partisan. It was appropriated by certain factions against others, like in the case of King Sverre to whom St Olaf handed his sword and banner to use against his rival for the throne, King Magnus Erlingsson (Lönnroth 2006, 606–607; Orning and Rosén 2021, 72–74).

St Adalbert’s spiritual and armed protection, in contrast, seems to have been less politically polarizing, as the quote from the *Gesta* shows. It was much more universal and collective, encompassing the Polish Christian community as a whole, which Gallus’s (2003, II.6.130–131) generic ‘in some castle of the Poles [in quoddam castrum Polonorum]’ suggests. Notably, the above episode is narrated apropos a story concerning the archiepiscopal church of Gniezno. The timing of St Adalbert’s apparition on a horse is thus not coincidental. It occurs ‘on the vigil of the dedication’ (Gallus 2003, II.6.130–131) of the cathedral and exactly a century after the martyr’s death (Holdsworth 1996, 106–107). In that sense, the miracle had a role to legitimize the institution, thus connecting the patron saint’s protection of the Poles with his and their archiepiscopal see (Prautzsch 2021, 26–27; Wiszewski 2010, 264–265).

Subsequent Polish chroniclers like Master Vincentius called Kadłubek (1994, IV.18.166), later bishop of Kraków, (r. 1208–1218) presented St Adalbert’s patronage and heroic status in his *Chronica Polonorum* (written c. 1190–1208) in an expanded, national frame. By decoupling the saint from Gniezno to some extent, the chronicler turned him

into the 'holiest patron of the Poles', who protected the entire Polish community (Kersken 2006, 177–178). By the Late Middle Ages, St Adalbert, sometimes accompanied by St Stanislaus, no longer only rendered military assistance in battles against pagans but also against the Teutonic Knights. St Adalbert accompanied the Polish troops at the battles of Płowce (1331) and Grunwald (1410), a clear sign of the growing nationalization of the saint in connection with warfare (Janicki 2010, 91, 107). This was on a par with the evolving national cults of other holy rulers, such as St Olaf or St Erik of Sweden (Mortensen 2010; Oertel 2016, 167, 200–211).

Holy stranger-king Adalbert heads to Gniezno

This special relationship between St Adalbert and the Polish people was mediated by the archbishopric of Gniezno and, crucially, not by the local rulers whose role is conspicuously obscured in these later pieces of hagiography vis-à-vis that in the *Passio from Tegernsee's* version. This relationship is at the heart of my argument that during his legendary visit to Poland the saint became a special variant of the stranger-king. To set the relevant episode from the *Tempore illo* in its proper context, we need to first briefly reconstruct the saint's historical as well as mythical itineraries in Poland.

In factual terms, based on the information from the *Vita prior* (2013, 27–30.168–181) and Bruno of Querfurt's (1969, 24–34.29–41) *Vita altera*, we know that after St Adalbert was permitted to preach to the pagans and after he received Duke Bolesław I's backing in Gniezno, the missionary and his two followers first arrived at the port city of Gdańsk. After they had baptized the local pagans, the company continued eastward to some Prussian tribes where the bishop died a martyr's death in April 997. In mythical terms, according to the *Tempore illo* that is, St Adalbert's travels looked quite different. Before the holy man came to Poland, he reached the semi-pagan shores of the Baltic Sea first. Furthermore, in between his journey to Gdańsk and later to Prussia, the anonymous author squeezed in the future martyr's two fabricated solitary journeys: first to Gniezno, where he would eventually meet Duke Bolesław I, and then to Pomerania. The description of the travel to Gniezno through the Polish countryside features a number of St Adalbert's missionary hardships and emphasizes his otherness in direct interactions with the Poles: this serves to establish his independent political relations with the populace, unmediated by the local ruler. It is during this journey that the holy man became a stranger-king for the first time.

As the heroic 'athlete of Christ' was travelling through Poland he arrived at a village where he asked some peasants for the way to Gniezno. However,

the inhabitants of this place, hearing how much his speech differed from the Polish, could not contain their laughter or derision ["nec a risu nec a derisu se continent"], especially when they saw his monastic clothes, something they had never seen before ["eum veste indutum pro monstro spectarent"] (*Tempore illo* 1888, 10.1181).

They flatly refused to speak to him and did not give him any directions. To this, though 'not ignited by anger, but by the holy spirit' St Adalbert responded: 'Because you do not want to speak for God's honour, for His honour I command you: stay silent!' After his departure, the peasants found themselves unable to open their mouths or speak and sorely regretted deriding him (*Tempore illo* 1888, 10.1181; Grzesik 1990). The same

scene was repeated in the next village: St Adalbert was similarly ‘loathed [“itidem contemptui habitus”], and received without any kindness [“humanitas”],’ again, leaving the obnoxious mute peasants behind (*Tempore illo* 1888, 10.1181). It was only in the third village that helpful and kind peasants showed the saint the way to Gniezno. There the bishop preached and performed miracles and the fame of his sanctity soon reached the mute peasants’ ears. They hurried to Gniezno, ‘fell to his feet, and through tears, sighs, and various gestures begged his pardon’ (*Tempore illo* 1888, 10.1181). In exchange for this submission, St Adalbert forgave them and restored their speech, after which the peasants immediately asked to be baptized. The holy man granted their wish and, incited by their compunction, instituted an unusually long nine-week fast (rather than the customary seven) preceding Easter.

As it has been argued elsewhere, this prolonged nine-week fast – an actual example of an exceptionally radical religious policy introduced in Poland by Bolesław I Chrobry in the early eleventh century, but not by St Adalbert decades earlier – in the *Tempore illo* becomes the fundamental lasting sign of this transformed relationship between the holy man and the Polish people (Jeziński 2019, 247–255; Michałowski 2004). The anonymous author turns the imposition of this new law into a mythopoetic (Mortensen 2006) moment:

They accepted this precept most eagerly; willingly observed it in their own lives and took care so that their descendants also observed it. For this reason, until today people all over Poland most piously and inviolately observe this rule, as if it was instituted by the apostles [‘quasi ab apostolis id traditum sit’], although this consists only of abstaining from eating meat for two weeks preceding Lent. (*Tempore illo* 1888, 10.1181-1182)

As we see, St Adalbert is repeatedly presented as an intercessor and the instrument of divine intervention,² who re-establishes the *humanitas*, that is, both kindness and the very humanity (Koselleck 2004, 157–184) of his new subjects. His miracles and preaching also privilege Gniezno (Sosnowski 2016) as the centre and the apostolic rock of Poland. Just like ‘the apostles and prophets’, St Adalbert also personally appoints his successor in Gniezno, his brother Radim Gaudentius (Kersken 2006, 170–172).³ The *Miracula* (1883, 4.31) embellishes on these details, and counterfactually presents the saint as the person who converted the Poles: ‘Thanks to God’s spirit speaking and working his many miracles through St Adalbert, the whole of Poland accepted the Christian faith.’

Though this invented travel episode has attracted the attention of scholars, so far no one has offered a compelling interpretation of the incivility of the peasants in the first two villages, which sets in motion the sequence of events leading to the Gniezno meeting and the establishment of a social contract between the holy man and the populace (Grzesik 1990; Gromadzki 1989, 36–37, 51, 58–59; Spież 1997, 189 n.37). What is the peasants’ rude reaction to St Adalbert’s speech and clothes supposed to mean? What sort of political implications does their cruel laughter and boorish behaviour have? And why can the Polish peasants not speak? It is my contention that one should put aside the simplistic explanation of this being the staple motif of how pagan communities reacted to the strange clothes and speech of missionaries known from many conversion narratives (Kujawiński 2004; Wood 2001, 220, 235, 239–240, 252, 258–259). Yes, the *Tempore illo* does use the *topos* of the otherness of missionaries, but it is for very specific political purposes. The question is: for which?

Let us return to Fiji and Polynesia and translate this mythical *hero's journey* by using the stranger-king concept. In order to present St Adalbert as a person who dominated the Poles, the authors of the *Tempore illo* purposefully estrange or *other* the saint from the autochthonous population. St Adalbert is not just an *other*. He is both *strange* (in terms of dress and speech) and a *stranger* who comes from *elsewhere* (de Heusch 1991). The rudeness and xenophobia of the Polish peasants as well as their initial rejection of the holy man make perfect structural sense as a mythical crisis (Graeber and Sahlins 2017, 147–150, 412–415). The road through Poland towards Gniezno becomes ‘the advent of the chief’, in Sahlins’s parlance (2008, 178–181; see also: Sahlins 1981, 111; Graeber and Sahlins 2017, 160–169), a ‘terrible epiphany’, which is in equal parts a symbolic conquest and a *mission civilisatrice*. It is the coming of a stranger-king – or stranger-bishop, as it were – who tames ‘the pre-social, anti-social dispositions of the native people’, in this case by making them speechless before he converts them (Graeber and Sahlins 2017, 153–155; Sahlins 2008, 179, 183–185).

What exactly are the anti-social dispositions of the Polish peasants? The scene in the village is an echo of the asking-the-way-motif which proliferated in the contemporary courtly literature in neighbouring Germany and elsewhere. As Michael Toch (1986, 667–672; Reuter 2006, 119–121) has shown, in Gottfried von Strasburg’s *Tristan*, Wolfram von Eschenbach’s *Parzival*, and other romances the scenes where lords asked peasants for directions reiterated the radical asymmetry between lords and peasants, and essentially reinforced the social order. On such occasions the lords, assuming violent poses and intimidating tones, took the initiative for the verbal exchange. The peasants, in turn, were expected to be useful, docile and – importantly – taciturn. In the scene from the *Tempore illo*, St Adalbert thus acts like a heroic errant knight, but his lordly status signalled by his dress is misrecognized by the Polish peasants who fail to show him proper deference. The peasants not just seem to address him at their leisure. They also make him a laughing stock based on both his clothing – or costume, if you like – and his Czech speech (de Heusch 1991, 111).⁴ This act of derision (Ferm 2002, 88–91, 159–227), in combination with the holy man’s ability to violently retaliate, makes St Adalbert an ambivalent figure very similar to the equally threatening god-like clowns in the Californian societies, studied by Graeber, who ‘appear to have represented the divine principle in general. Rather than humans impersonating gods, they were gods impersonating humans.’⁵

The form of this retaliation and punishment through wondrous muteness which reinstates the social order on the occasion of Christianization, in turn, is strongly reminiscent of the confrontation between King Olaf I Tryggvason and farmers in Rogaland in Western Norway at the famous *ping* meeting in the late tenth century, which was depicted, by among others, in ‘Oláfs saga Tryggvasonar’ in Snorri Sturluson’s *Heimskringla* (1941, 1:55.305–306). There the supposedly three most eloquent local leaders and farmers are miraculously left coughing, stammering and with hoarse throats, incapable of articulating their refusal to agree to the conversion of their region (Antonsson 2010, 22–23). It is worth keeping in mind that even in purely imaginary terms the powerful freeholding farmers of late-Viking-Age Norway (even when projected from Snorri’s thirteenth-century perspective) were nothing like the serf-like peasants in twelfth-century Poland. Still, in both miraculous stories these two distinct types of subalterns cannot speak (Spivak 1994) for the very same reasons: their speech is taken away through the awe of seeing these powerful missionary figures. In contrast to the missionary and quasi-holy

King Olaf Tryggvason who imposes the new creed with threats and brute force and is an autochthonous king, St Adalbert is explicitly depicted in both the *Tempore illo* and the *Miracula* as an unarmed yet still socially superior and, thanks to the divine power invested in him, powerful stranger (Prautzsch 2021, 16–18).

The political relationship St Adalbert offers to his soon-to-be diocesans is accordingly not a unilateral imposition like in King Olaf's case, but a reciprocal, deeply dialectical contract. In the process, the offended and abused (through ridicule) stranger-king is domesticated and naturalized by his freshly tamed local subjects (Graeber and Sahlins 2017, 169–175; Jezierski 2019, 252–255; Sahlins 2008, 183). This is not achieved through marriage with the daughters of the land of course, as in the examples discussed by Sahlins (2008, 178). His domestication is achieved instead through the fictionally antedated institutionalization of the Gniezno archbishopric, the saint's house at the centre of his ecumene, to which he is brought from the periphery of the countryside.⁶ It is in equal parts a house and a monument (*pace* Dobat), which the saint himself founds with his miracles and then leaves – as an absent sovereign – always already handed over to his successor and kinsman Radim Gaudentius (Diem 2007, 546–558; Graeber and Sahlins 2017, 184–185).⁷ In Sahlins's idiom, it is a foundation of an archiepiscopal dynasty by immigrants – obviously short-lasting and biologically infertile due to the incumbents' vows of clerical celibacy.

What is at stake in this political myth is therefore a transformation of the form of legitimacy, from a charismatic one that is executed through exceptional miracles to a bureaucratic one that is routinely administered through pastoral care. This legitimacy is also transferred from the transient holy man to the situated, permanent holy institution (Diem 2007, 523–527, 542–546; Graeber and Sahlins 2017, 161–163; Prautzsch 2021, 160–163, 271–274; Weber 1978, vol. 1, 36–38, 241–254, vol. 2, 1141–1148). The covenant between the powerful foreigner St Adalbert and the locals – symbolized by the baptism and forever commemoratively reproduced by the prolonged fast, effectively a new religious law and order brought and instituted by the stranger, as Sahlins (1981, 113) would have it – clearly turns out to be beneficial for the Poles. It is a privilege which marks the transformed people as not just wholly Christian, but also unusually pious in comparison with other nations. The covenant also bestows legitimacy and extraordinary symbolic capital on the covenant's local custodians, the archbishops of Gniezno (Cole 2020, 205–209; Michałowski 2004, 7–10, 46–47).

Interestingly, the nature of this religiopolitical covenant is further qualified during the subsequent, equally fictional journey of St Adalbert to Pomerania. It provides an occasion for the reader to entertain a counterfactual idea about who the saint could have been but decided not to.⁸ There St Adalbert is said to have baptized the local pagan prince, who intended to marry the daughter of the Polish king. This suggests not just the marital availability of Sahlins's 'daughters of the land' and Polish society's openness to alterity, which the stranger-bishop could not just mediate but also functionally complete, thus enhancing the Polish ruler's power. All of this came to naught, however, as the Pomeranian prince's subjects proved inconvertible. They were offended by the holy man's blasphemous teachings which suggested their deities were false. Instead of letting themselves be converted, however, the Pomeranians 'humbly besought the man of God to allow them to venerate him as god and not refuse to be worshipped together with their other gods' (*Tempore illo* 1888, 12.1182). St Adalbert, however, rejected their offer with

tears: 'You miserable people (...) want to ascribe deity not just to demons but to mortal men ["sed etiam mortalibus deitatem vultis ascribere"], which is appropriate only to God who created everything!' (*Tempore illo* 1888, 12.1182). Rather than become a human impersonating a god, St Adalbert chooses to remain a holy man and a stranger-bishop impersonating a king.

St Adalbert's eventual martyrdom at the hands of the Prussians and his disappearance as a living person hence receives a new significance motivated by a mythological necessity in the *Tempore illo*. The saint is no longer simply killed as a Prussian sacrificial victim, which is almost coincidental to some extent as in the *Vita prior* (Banaszkiewicz 2014, 307–310). Instead, his death scene follows the *Vita altera*, where Bruno of Querfurt (1969, 24.62, 34.69) called the holy man a sacrificial host ('mactata hostia', 'hostia viva'), showcasing the eucharistic character of his martyrdom (Sosnowski 2013, 85–114; Figurski 2012, 76–80; Banaszkiwicz 2014, 310–314). In the *Tempore illo* too, St Adalbert performs an anticipated and self-fashioned Christomimetic self-sacrifice. Having waited for the appropriate hour on Friday so that he would suffer on the same day and time as Christ, St Adalbert 'approached the sacrifice [of the mass] of the body of Christ, as the sacrificial victim he himself was soon to become' (*Tempore illo* 1888, 15.1182). Just like the Polynesian chief, St Adalbert 'is his own sacrificial victim and lost god of his people' (Sahlins 1981, 122).⁹ This means that in the stranger-king logic that permeates the *Tempore illo*, the murderous Prussians (Prautzsch 2021, 149–152) to some extent play into the hands of the Polish people and finish the job symbolically started by the rude peasants. Bolesław I Chrobry's buying back of St Adalbert's corpse thus returns the stranger-king's carcass to its proper owners, beneficiaries and subjects: the Poles.¹⁰

A great man in Lesser Poland, a lesser man in Greater Poland

If in the late-thirteenth-century *Miracula sancti Adalberti* (1883, 4.31) the prolonged fast was still commemorated – though no longer followed, since it had been cancelled by a papal legate in 1248 (Jeziński 2019, 253; Michałowski 2004, 46–49; Kersken 2006) – it had fallen into oblivion by the mid-fifteenth century. St Adalbert's otherness as the precondition and essence of the relationship between him and the Polish people did not, however. In his *Annals*, Jan Długosz revisited the fable of St Adalbert's journey through the Polish countryside, which the *Tempore illo* had invented, but he gave it several fantastic twists of his own (Węcowski 2014, 311–313).

The holy man, arriving in Poland from Hungary, conveniently visited Kraków first. There, at the city market the bishop 'devoted himself to the pious obligation of preaching in his Bohemian mother tongue, well understood by the Poles' (Długosz 1964, II.213). His public teaching attracted crowds from the surrounding countryside. People flocked not just to receive his consolation. Some demon-possessed locals approached him as well, giving the bishop a chance to perform miraculous exorcisms. Upon his departure,

St Adalbert left such good a memory of his teachings, actions, and merits of life in the city of Kraków, that after the fulfillment of his glorious martyrdom a church was erected in his honor on the spot where he had used to preach, which to this day remains as a testimony of the care the God's man took for disseminating the word of life and the devotion shown to him by the Poles. (Długosz 1964, II.213)

From the capital of Lesser Poland the holy man and his companions hastened to Gniezno, where they, counterfactually again, met Duke Mieszko I (who died in 992) and his son Bolesław I. On their way there, the bishop preached and taught people in every village he came across. However, 'one day, when he got lost, he entered a certain village in Greater Poland, where the peasants laughed at his and his companions' monastic habit and hoods, which they had never seen before, taking them for madmen ["pro insanis eos reputantibus"]' (Długosz 1964, II.213–214). The deriders soon met a divine punishment, becoming both mute and deaf. St Adalbert restored these faculties to the peasants after they came to Gniezno and publicly confessed their crime.

Like other high- and late-medieval Polish chroniclers (Węcowski 2014, 297–321), Długosz told the story of St Adalbert's visit to Poland primarily as a way to distance the holy man from the loathsome and ungrateful Bohemians and to showcase the pious hospitality in Poland. What is remarkable about these two radically opposed receptions presented here is that even in the fifteenth century the otherness of the holy man still retained a xenopolitical potency and foundational function (Heidenreich 2011, 179–180; Wellendorf 2022a, 523–524). In contrast to the author of the *Tempore illo*, however, the chronicler applies two contradictory strategies for how he depicts the saint's travels and his relationship with the local populations in different parts of Poland. Długosz is simultaneously *othering* St Adalbert (through clothing) in relation to the rude peasants from Greater Poland and *sameing* him (through language) with respect to the people of Lesser Poland, to employ Clemens Gantner's (2021, 93–95) distinction. Through this rhetorical reversal, splitting and ultimate fusion, St Adalbert chokes on his cake and keeps it too. He is presented both as a chicaned clown-like but still threatening stranger-king (Graeber and Sahlins 2017, 396–397, 411–412) in Greater Poland, and as a familiar, almost autochthonous, and fully comprehensible holy man in Kraków, that is, in the city and diocese whose interests the chronicler represents.

The only monuments that commemorate the holy man and his charisma, as the story records, are those erected in Kraków; characteristically there are none in Gniezno, despite it noting his preaching there. In Greater Poland, counterfactually, St Adalbert is said to have come to an already established archiepiscopal see – an institution which he merely takes over after a recently deceased incumbent, a fictional figure, whom the chronicler presents as Archbishop Robert, who is implicitly of local origin. This means that the powerful stranger is merely added to a pre-existing institutional genealogy and does not get to appoint his successor (Długosz 1964, II.214). All Poles are already converted so there is no need for any new covenant or law and, consequently, for any new monuments to commemorate it either. The Kraków monuments, on the other hand, do not celebrate St Adalbert as an immigrant founder, but only as a saint in the bishopric which by the fifteenth century had long overshadowed that of Gniezno in terms of both influence and political standing. This retroactive mythological appropriation of the holy man is hence a seizure not of the institutional legitimacy, but only of his symbolic capital and prestige for the bishops of Kraków (Węcowski 2014, 312). Following Claude Lévi-Strauss (1966, 161–162, 165–173), Graeber and Sahlins (2017, 411–412) we could say that Długosz's *particularizing*, tribalizing gesture of transferring St Adalbert as a local totem from Gniezno to Kraków is the final move in a long process of annexation of the saint's image, which was initiated at least two and a half centuries earlier by Master Vincentius through the *universalization* of the saint as a national patron.

Conclusion

Let me return to the opening riddle and the solution proposed by Gieysztor. The Piasts may not have sanctified any member of their dynasty, as was the case for other peripheral polities, but this does not mean that Poland did not have a holy ruler. St Adalbert did not just occupy the position of a patron saint, because he was a martyr, missionary, bishop, monk and aristocrat. He also did so because his mythologized persona appropriated traits of the stranger-kingship on the basis of entering a series of political relationships with the local populace that hinged on his ethnic and sacral otherness. In the imagination of his Polish high- and late-medieval custodians and confessors, now and then St Adalbert behaved quite *like* a king – *like* a warrior king, *like* a holy stranger-king and *like* an absent immigrant sovereign. To reiterate: the saint never received such a title nor demonstrated any explicit royal attributes. And yet the bishop's undeniable heroization (in ever-shifting local, national and universal frames) and his stranger-king status can inspire us to extend the class of peripheral holy rulers to encompass even such complex typological hybrids and allochthonous figures like St Adalbert as outlier, critical cases which conformed to or mimicked the holy ruler phenomenon in innovative ways (Flyvbjerg 2001, 77–81; Bhabha 2004, 121–131; Michałowski and Pac 2020; Klaniczay 2010, 303–304). By insisting on the sacral and supernatural elements in St Adalbert's sainthood the texts studied here seemed to creatively discuss with the Gelasian principle that separated religious authority from political power in a context where no figure of holy king did that (Nelson 1973, 40–42). For such reassessments of these medievalist concepts and distinctions the inspiration and comparative material from anthropology are indispensable.

It is no coincidence that the sources where St Adalbert is most explicitly presented as a stranger-king – the *Tempore illo* and the *Miracula sancti Adalberti* – come from the twelfth and thirteenth centuries. It was in this period that the formal division and fragmentation of the Polish realm (1138–1295), characterized by the absence of royal authority (restored in 1295, 1300 and lastingly in 1320), the very weak power of senior princes, and the ever-growing multitude of independent dukedoms, took place (Berend, Urbańczyk, and Wiszewski 2013, 174–176, 242–243, 367–369). This was also a period in which the ideological and political standing of the Polish episcopate grew. This resulted, particularly in the second half of the thirteenth century, in the promotion of the idea of the restoration of a unified kingdom and kingship itself by heavily politicizing the cults of Poland's patron saints, St Stanislaus (an autochthonous saint) and St Adalbert (a saint whose allochthony was suddenly inflated), through their nationalization and universalization (Mrozowicz 1999; Labuda 2000; Drelicharz 2012, 241–268). In the absence of autochthonous kings, a mythical stranger-king rose to power. For Długosz, on the other hand, St Adalbert's stranger-kingship lost most of its political potential. This is hardly surprising given that the clerical chronicler was a tutor in history to several Jagiellonian monarchs and had witnessed the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth reach its apex. In the fifteenth century St Adalbert's otherness was still an exciting source of symbolic capital and a means of local institutional distinction, but his role as a royal substitute was no longer central.

The comparison between the opposing ways of othering/sameing St Adalbert and the different degrees to which the saint was presented as a stranger-king in Długosz's *Annales vis-à-vis Tempore illo* and the *Miracula sancti Adalberti* is an opportune occasion for a broader contemplation of the role otherness and the foreign played as ambiguous

sources of power in the Middle Ages and for our ways of explaining it. By exploring the ways in which the otherness of ruling figures was enhanced, supplemented, or even completely invented in the stories and monuments that commemorate their rule we can better understand both the native and more widely shared notions of kingship and the origins of dynasties and the varying ways of claiming legitimacy and their similarities and occasional interchangeability with episcopal authority. These included not only those that circulated on the North-eastern peripheries, but others in medieval Europe more generally. In that way, even such ambivalent just-so stories and seemingly derivative pieces of hagiography like the later *vitae* of St Adalbert can be read as situated political treatises and manifestos debating the tenets of the ruling ideology and social order communicated through their most elementary symbolic forms (Eagleton 1988, 327–338; Weiler 2015; Orning and Rosén 2021; Graeber and Wengrow 2021, 93–97, 112–113, 205–209). As Sahlins put it:

Social scientists often see in all this a mystification of power, framed in the interests of the rulers. Yet as a ‘dominant ideology’ it is at least equivocal, since as in the instance of Captain Cook, or anthropological analogues of the Priest of Nemi, it may also authorize the people to ‘sit upon the ground and tell sad tales of the death of kings’. But to speak of an interested ideology in the first place is to sadly impoverish the description of these facts. The rationalization of power is not at issue so much as the representation of a general scheme of social life: a total ‘structure of reproduction’, including the complementary and antithetical relations between king and people, god and man, male and female, foreign and native, war and peace, heavens and earth. (Sahlins 1981, 114)

Notes

1. It still remains to be investigated if the elevation of St Adalbert to the position of patron saint constitutes an outlier against the peripheral background populated by holy kings, or whether the Polish case is an extension of older Western tendencies to elevate holy bishops to such positions and that, in fact, the peripheral holy rulers collectively constitute an exception against the widened European context (Michałowski 2005; Pac 2016, 106–110).
2. *Tempore illo* (1888, 9.1180–1181): ‘non ira conmotus, sed Spiritu sancto’; ‘Deo per servum suum iubente’; ‘per suum famulum Christus’; ‘Unde ego servus eius (...) in eiusdem nomine Ihesu Christ, videlicet domini nostri Creatoris omnium’; ‘fidelis dispensator Christi’.
3. *Tempore illo* (1888, 11.1182): ‘Sancto igitur Spiritu per famulum suum predicante multaque illic signa mirabiliter faciente, christianam legem Polonia gratanter universa suscipit, sanctique instituta viri ovanter amplectens, supra firmam petram fundari meruit. *Vir namque sanctus fundamentum apostolorum et prophetarum ibi stabilire cupiens*, quendam christianissimum virum, sui socium laboris et itineris, Gaudencium nomine ibidem archiepiscopum pro se constituit, quia ipse videlicet ad alias regiones paganorum festinabat, quas lucrifacere Christo nichilominus anelabat’; 20.1184: ‘desiderabiles reliquias 8. Idus Novembris in metropolim sollempnissime transtulit ubi ad eius tumulum quam plurima divinitus per eum parantur beneficia omnibus’. Emphasis mine.
4. It has been suggested that the saint’s newfound linguistic otherness reflects actual or imagined confrontations between Polish peasants and Bohemians contemporary with the composition of the source, which would add a sociolinguistic dimension on top of the anthropological reading of this scene.
5. Graeber and Sahlins (2017, 383): ‘Clowns were also the only figures in those rituals (...) who had the power to issue direct orders to anyone else’, 384: ‘Clown commands were supposed to be whimsical – hence, arbitrary – but clown commands were the only genuine commands anyone gave or received in most Californian societies, since only they were enforced by the

- threat of sanction. What's more, the clowns were not, like the costumed masqueraders, identified with specific gods, they appear to have represented the divine principle in general. Rather than humans impersonating gods, they were gods impersonating humans.' 382–388.
6. Sahlins (1981, 127): 'Having moved from the sea to the land, the foreign to the indigenous, the chief is now encompassed by the people. True, the axis of his divinity rotates from the earthly plane to a position above: gifts of mats brought by people of the land make up his elevated seat upon the ceremonial ground. But at the same time, he has been domesticated and humanized, brought from the natural periphery of society to its centre.'
 7. Sahlins (1981, 122): 'The Fijian chief is both invading male and (...) notorious cannibal on the one hand, whose anger (*cudru*) is always feared, he is on the other hand immobilized: he 'just sits' Fijians say – i.e. in the house, as a woman – 'and the things are brought to him.'"
 8. Hacking (2002, 107): 'Who we are is not only what we did, do, and will do, but also what we might have done and may do.'
 9. Sahlins (1981, 124): 'The death of the king is thus the moment of his re-ascension, of his reconquest of the land and the incorporation of his divine predecessor, so in the end it is the god Lono who is sacrificed. Just as the provisional king of carnival must eventually suffer execution, the image of the returned god is soon after dismantled, bound and hidden away.'
 10. Sahlins (1981, 127): 'Taken in war from beyond the land (*vanua*), in the privileged instances from notorious warriors and chiefs of rebellious subjects or traditional enemies, such victims are of the nature of the chief himself – terrible outside gods. The chief, poisoned and reborn as a domestic god, must now give feast to the people *on bodies of his own kind*.' Emphasis mine.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank Grzegorz Pac (Warsaw) and Gustavs Strenga (Greifswald) for their comments on earlier drafts of this article.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

The research leading to these results has received funding from two sources: the Norwegian Financial Mechanism 2014–2021 (2019/34/H/HS3/00500) and the Swedish Research Council (VR 2020-01810). This article is part of a joint research project of the University of Warsaw and the University of Oslo 'Symbolic Resources and Political Structures on the Periphery: Legitimization of the ELITES in Poland and Norway, c. 1000-1300' and 'Ambiguities of Hospitality: Intercultural Integration and Conflict in Host–Guest Relations on the European Borderlands, c. 1000-1350' project conducted at the Department of Historical Studies, University of Gothenburg.

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